

The type material of Isostictidae, Dicteriadidae, Argiolestidae and Megapodagrionidae in the Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin (Odonata)

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Received 14th September 2016; revised and accepted 20th June 2017

Abstract. A catalogue listing all species-group names associated with type specimens of the families Isostictidae, Dicteriadidae, Argiolestidae and Megapodagrionidae (Odonata) currently housed in the entomological collection of the Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science in Berlin (Germany) – includes current status of the species-group names, transcriptions of data labels and references to the original descriptions.

Further key words. Dragonfly, damselfly, Zygoptera, catalogue, collection locality, collector, verbatim label, type

Introduction

Following publication on the type material of Calopterygidae in the Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin, Germany (TURIAULT 2016), I here treat representatives of the families Isostictidae Fraser, 1955, Argiolestidae Fraser, 1957, Dicteriadidae Montgomery, 1959 and Megapodagrionidae Calvert, 1913. I have chosen to follow the classification suggested by DIJKSTRA et al. (2013) and KALKMAN & THEISCHINGER (2013). This project was undertaken in order to provide curatorial information for taxonomists in accordance with Recommendation 74G of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. No lectotypes have been designated since »lectotype designations should be done as part of a revisionary or other taxonomic work in order to enhance the stability of nomenclature, and not for mere curatorial convenience« (ICZN 1999).

Only a small number of photographs of type material accompanies this paper (Figs 1–4); the remainder can be accessed on the internet (<http://www.digicoll.info/search>).

MNB – Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin, Germany.

List of species-group names bearing type material

ISOSTICTIDAE

Original combination: *Isosticta filiformis* Ris, 1898

Status: available species-group name, valid species

Current combination: *Tanymecosticta filiformis* (Ris, 1898)

Type material. One male; collection locality: river Matanata, Ralum, New Britain, Bismarck Archipelago; collector: Friedrich Dahl

Verbatim label data male 78c171: (1) »Neu-Britannien / Ralum / F. Dahl S.« [printed]; (2) »Type« [printed]; (3) »Matanata / Fluß / 3.2.97« [handwritten]; (4) »Isosticta / filiformis Ris / nov. spec.« [handwritten]; (5) »Tanymecosticta / filiformis (Ris)« [handwritten] / »det. M. A. Lieftinck 19« [printed], »38« [handwritten]; (6) »http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/78c171« [printed].

Notes: The information accompanying the original description includes: »5. *Isosticta filiformis* nov. spec. 1♂.«, »Hinterleib metallgrün, der Bauch und die Seiten der ersten zwei Segmente weisslich (Segm. 7-10 fehlen). Abdomen (Segm. 1-6) 28+?, Hfl. 20 mm.«. The description is based on one male, which is consequently the holotype.

DICTERIADIDAE

Original combination: *Heliocharis brasiliensis* Hagen in Selys, 1859

Status: available species-group name, junior synonym

Current combination: *Heliocharis amazona* Selys, 1853

Type material. One male; collection locality: Bahia, Brazil; collector: M. Böck

Verbatim label data male 4a950e: (1) »3400« [printed]; (2) »Typus« [printed]; (3) »Heliocharis / brasiliensis.« [handwritten]; (4) »Bahia Böck« [handwritten]; (5) »Heliocharis brasiliensis Hagen« [printed]; (6) »Zoolog. Museum / BERLIN (ZMB) / Germany« [printed]; (7) »http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a950e« [printed].

Notes: Hagen's original description states: »♀ Inconnue.«, »Patrie: Bahia. (Musée de Berlin. Envoi de M. Boeck.)«. The description thus seems to be based on a single male; the specimen in MNB is the holotype.

Figure 1. *Heliogaris brasiliensis* Hagen in Selys, 1859, synonym of *Heliogaris amazona* Selys, 1853; male holotype in coll. MNB (♂ 4a950e), lateral view.

Figure 2. *Heliogaris brasiliensis* Hagen in Selys, 1859, synonym of *Heliogaris amazona* Selys, 1853; labels of male holotype in coll. MNB (♂ 4a950e).

ARGIOLESTIDAE

Original combination: *Argiolestes aurantiaca* Ris, 1898

Status: available species-group name, valid species

Current combination: *Metagrion aurantiacum* (Ris, 1898)

Type material. Two males; collection locality: Lowon, Ralum, New Britain, Bismarck Archipelago; collector: Friedrich Dahl

Verbatim label data male 4a9538: (1) »[illegible] / [illegible] / Quelle im / oberen Lowon / 7.1.97« [handwritten]; (2) »Neu-Britannien / Ralum / F. Dahl S.« [printed]; (3) »Zoolog. Museum / BERLIN (ZMB) / Germany« [printed]; (4) »Argiolestes / aurantiaca Ris« [handwritten]; (5) »http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a9538« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a9537: (1) »[illegible] / [illegible] / [illegible] / [illegible]. Quelle im / oberen Lowon / 7.1.97« [handwritten]; (2) »Neu-Britannien / Ralum / F. Dahl S.« [printed]; (3) »Zoolog. Museum / BERLIN (ZMB) / Germany« [printed]; (4) »Argiolestes / aurantiaca Ris / nov. spec.« [handwritten]; (5) »10« [handwritten]; (6) »Type« [printed]; (7) »http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a9537« [printed].

Notes: Supplementary information accompanying the original description includes: »4. *Argiolestes aurantiaca* nov. spec. 2♂.«. First, one adult male is described in detail, then a freshly emerged male: »Das eine, ganz frisch ausgeschlüpfte Exempl. [...]«. The two males are considered syntypes.

MEGAPODAGRIONIDAE

Original combination: *Amphilestes mima* Karsch, 1891

Status: available species-group name, valid species

Current combination: *Rhinagrion mima* (Karsch, 1891)

Type material. One male; collecting locality: Deli, Sumatra; collector: L. Martin

Verbatim label data male 4a9536: (1) »6580« [printed]; (2) »Typus« [printed]; (3) »Deli Sumatra / L. Martin G.« [printed]; (4) »Amphilestes / mima / n.sp. / Karsch *« [handwritten]; (5) »http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a9536« [printed].

Notes: Karsch described »1♂«. KALKMAN & VILLANUEVA (2011) wrote »*Rhinagrion mima* was described by KARSCH (1891) based on one male from Bindjei (Deli) from the Indonesian island of Sumatra.«. The specimen is the holotype.

Figure 3. *Amphilestes mima* Karsch, 1891; male holotype in coll. MNB (♂ 4a9536), dorsal view.

Original combination: *Rhipidolestes truncatidens* Schmidt, 1931

Status: available species-group name, valid species

Current combination: *Rhipidolestes truncatidens* Schmidt, 1931

Type material. Six males; collection locality: Canton & Tscha-jiu-san, China; collector: Rudolf Mell

Verbatim label data male 4a9533: (1) »373« [printed]; (2) »China, Canton, / 1. I. 12, [crossed out] / Mell S. V.« [printed]; (3) »[chinese symbols]« [handwritten]; (4) »Syntypus« [printed]; (5) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (6) »fotografiert! / siehe Literatur S. 182« [handwritten]; (7) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a9533>« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a952b: (1) »374« [printed]; (2) »China - Canton / Mell S. V.« [printed]; (3) »Syntypus« [printed]; (4) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (5) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a952b>« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a952f: (1) »375« [printed]; (2) »China - Canton / Mell S V.« [printed]; (3) »V, T. J. S. N° 78« [handwritten]; (4) »Syntypus« [printed]; (5) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (6) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a952f>« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a952c: (1) »380« [printed]; (2) »China, Canton, / 1. I. [crossed out] 12, / Mell S. V.« [printed]; (3) »[chinese symbols]« [handwritten]; (4) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (5) »Syntypus« [printed]; (6) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a952c>« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a952e: (1) »376« [printed]; (2) »China, / Tsha-jiu-san, / 6. V. 11, / Mell S. V.« [printed]; (3) »N° 81 / (ähnl. 27.« [handwritten]; (4) »Libelle, Mai 11, T. J. S« [handwritten]; (5) »N. 81 / (ähnl = 27)« [handwritten]; (6) »Rhipidolestes / acutidens ♂ / n. sp. Typen« [handwritten], / »det. Dr. Erich Schmidt 19« [printed], »31« [handwritten]; (7) »Syntypus« [printed]; (8) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (9) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a952e>« [printed].

Verbatim label data male 4a952d: (1) »378« [printed]; (2) »China, / Tsha-jiusan, / 6. V. 11, / Mell S. V.« [printed]; (3) »N° 48« [handwritten]; (4) »Nr. 78« [handwritten]; (5) »Mai 11, Tsha J. S.« [handwritten]; (6) »Syntypus« [printed]; (7) »Rhipidolestes / truncatidens / Schmidt / 1931« [handwritten]; (8) »<http://coll.mfn-berlin.de/u/4a952d>« [printed].

Notes: Schmidt only described male characteristics and mentioned: »Material: 6♂, leg. Dr. Mell, davon 4♂ Canton, bezeichnet 373, 374, 375, 380; 2♂ Tsha-jiusan, 6. V. 11, bezeichnet 376, 378.« and »Typen im Zool. Museum der Universität Berlin.«. The mentioned specimens are syntypes.

Figure 4. *Rhipidolestes truncatidens* Schmidt, 1931; male syntype in coll. MNB (♂ 4a952e), dorsal view.

Acknowledgments

Because they helped me as they did it for my last paper on the type material of *Calopterygidae*, I would like to thank sincerely the Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin, especially PD Dr Michael Ohl, as well as Mirko Lange, Sebastian Demtröder and Florian Weihrauch. This paper could not have been possible without the knowledge, patience and generosity of Rosser Garrison, who as always encouraged and guided me through this.

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